

THE MAIN LINGUACULTURAL FEATURES OF PROPER NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.

Ubaydullayeva Madina

a teacher of National

university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12204108>

Proper nouns in English and Uzbek share some similarities but also have distinct linguacultural features. In English, proper nouns typically start with a capital letter and are used to identify specific people, places, organizations, and things. They can be names of individuals (e.g., John, London), geographical locations (e.g., Pacific Ocean, Mount Everest), companies (e.g., Apple Inc.), and more. English proper nouns often reflect the cultural and historical background of the English-speaking world.

In Uzbek, proper nouns also start with a capital letter and serve a similar function of identifying specific entities. However, Uzbek proper nouns may reflect the cultural heritage and history of Uzbekistan and Central Asia. They can include personal names (e.g., Abdulla, Gulnara), place names (e.g., Tashkent, Samarkand), historical figures (e.g., Amir Timur), and cultural references unique to the Uzbek language and region.

Both English and Uzbek proper nouns play a crucial role in language by providing specificity and context to communication. They can offer insights into the cultural, historical, and social aspects of the communities where these languages are spoken.

Proper nouns in English and Uzbek exhibit distinct linguacultural features that reflect the history, culture, and societal norms of their respective language communities.

1. Diversity: English proper nouns are diverse, reflecting the multicultural nature of English-speaking societies. They include names from various linguistic origins, such as Latin (e.g., Julius Caesar), Germanic (e.g., William), and more.

2. Historical Significance: Many English proper nouns are rooted in historical events, figures, or places, providing a glimpse into the country's past. For example, names like Washington, Lincoln, and Shakespeare carry significant historical and cultural weight.

3. Influence of Colonization: English proper nouns may also reflect the influence of colonization, with names borrowed from colonized regions and countries worldwide. This mix of names contributes to the linguistic diversity of English.

1. Cultural Heritage: Uzbek proper nouns often reflect the rich cultural heritage of Uzbekistan and Central Asia. Names like Babur, Ulugbek, and Navoi are examples of prominent figures from Uzbek history and literature.

2. Geographical References: Many Uzbek proper nouns are tied to geographical locations within Uzbekistan and the broader Central Asian region. Place names like Bukhara, Khiva, and Fergana Valley are common examples.

3. Islamic Influence: Given Uzbekistan's historical ties to Islamic civilization, some proper nouns in Uzbek may have religious significance or Islamic origins. Names like Muhammad, Fatima, and Ali are examples of this influence.

4. Nomadic Traditions: Traditional Uzbek naming customs may also reflect nomadic traditions and cultural practices. For instance, names like Tursun, Gulnoza, and Bahrom are common in Uzbek culture.

Both English and Uzbek proper nouns play a crucial role in preserving and transmitting cultural identity. While English proper nouns showcase a diverse range of influences due to the language's global reach, Uzbek proper nouns highlight the unique heritage and traditions of Uzbekistan and Central Asia. Studying proper nouns in each language provides valuable insights into the linguistic, historical, and cultural landscapes of these distinct societies.

English Proper Nouns:

1. Etymological Diversity:

- English proper nouns often derive from various languages due to historical influences like invasions, colonization, and trade. This linguistic diversity enriches the English lexicon.

- Examples include names with Latin roots (e.g., Victoria), Germanic origins (e.g., Edward), French influences (e.g., Jacqueline), and more.

2. Socio-Cultural Significance:

- English proper nouns frequently reflect societal values, historical events, and cultural icons. Names like Churchill, Beatles, and Shakespeare carry immense cultural weight.

- Some names are associated with specific professions, titles, or social statuses, highlighting social hierarchies and traditions.

3. Globalization Impact:

- Due to globalization, English proper nouns increasingly incorporate names from diverse cultures and languages worldwide. This reflects the interconnected nature of the modern world.

- Names like Priyanka, Alejandro, and Ling reflect this global influence on English proper nouns.

1. Cultural Symbolism:

- Uzbek proper nouns often embody cultural symbols, historical figures, and literary references unique to Uzbekistan and Central Asia.

- Names like Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, and Babur hold significant cultural importance and historical resonance.

2. Nominal Patterns:

- Traditional Uzbek naming customs may follow specific patterns based on gender, family lineage, or regional traditions. These patterns contribute to the preservation of Uzbek cultural identity.

- Surnames in Uzbek culture often indicate tribal affiliations or ancestral ties, reflecting the importance of kinship and heritage.

3. Religious Influences:

- Islam plays a crucial role in Uzbek society, influencing naming practices and the selection of proper nouns. Names like Zaynab, Alijon, and Muhammadali are common examples reflecting Islamic heritage.

- Some Uzbek proper nouns may include religious titles or honorifics, emphasizing spiritual beliefs and values within the culture.

Proper nouns in English and Uzbek serve as linguistic artifacts that encapsulate historical narratives, cultural values, and societal norms. While English proper nouns showcase a globalized and diverse linguistic landscape, Uzbek proper nouns highlight the rich heritage, traditions, and religious influences specific to Uzbekistan and Central Asia. Studying these linguacultural features provides valuable insights into the identities and histories of these language communities.

The list of used literature:

1. Begmatov, E. O`zbek onomastikasi: bibliografik sharh. Toshkent, 2008.
2. Beletskiy, A.A Leksikologiya va nazariya tilshunoslik : onomastika. Kiev, 1989.
3. Reformatorskiy A.A.: Toponimika va transkripsiya. M : Nauka,1994
4. Superanskaya, A. V. Ismning umumiy nazariyasi M: Nauka,1993
5. Superanskaya, A. V. Terminologiya va onomastikai. Riga, 1993.